

PIC16F877A Microcontroller Using Automatic Green House Monitoring and Controlling System

MINI PROJECT REPORT

Final report

Engineering Research - Embedded Systems

EEE3305

Group Members:

1. S.S.R.De Silva – 21UG0450
2. K.G.H.P.R.Kodithuwakku – 21UG0435

Faculty of Engineering
SLTC Research University

January 2024

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT-----	3
CHAPTER 01 - INTRODUCTION-----	4
1.1 PROBLEM AND SOLUTION ENCOUNTERED ON GREEN HOUSE -----	4
CHAPTER 02 - LITERATURE SURVEY -----	5
CHAPTER 03 – METHODOLOGY -----	6
3.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DEVICE-----	6
3.2 HARDWARE DESCRIPTION-----	7
1. MICROCONTROLLER - PIC16F877A-----	7
2.SENSOR-----	7
3.RELAY -----	8
3.3 CIRCUIT DESIGN OF PROPOSED SYSTEM-----	9
3.4 PCB LAYOUT OF GREENHOUSE MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEM-----	11
3.5 SOFTWARES USED FOR DESIGN OF GREENHOUSE MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEM-----	12
3.6 WORKING OF GREENHOUSE MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEM-----	12
CHAPTER 04 - RESULTS AND DISCUSSION -----	14
4.1 TESTING AND RESULTS -----	14
I] SOFTWARE TESTING -----	14
II] HARDWARE TESTING -----	14
4.2 RESULTS-----	15
CHAPTER 05 - CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK -----	16
5.1 CONCLUSION-----	16
5.2 FUTURE WORK & CHALLENGES -----	16
APPENDIX (CODE)-----	17
REFERENCES-----	19

PIC16F877A Microcontroller Using Automatic Green House Monitoring and Controlling System

De Silva S.S.R¹, Kodithuwakku K.G.H.P.R²

¹Faculty of Engineering ,SLTC Research University ,Meepe,Sri Lanka,,21ug0450@sltc.ac.lk

²Faculty of Engineering ,SLTC Research University,Meepe,Sri Lanka,21ug0435@sltc.ac.lk

ABSTRACT

Greenhouses have emerged as pivotal tools in modern agriculture, fostering an environment where plants can flourish irrespective of external climatic conditions. This paper delves into the pivotal role of greenhouses and explores the efficacy of a sophisticated monitoring and control system in optimizing crop yield. The integration of a PIC Microcontroller and various sensors establishes a comprehensive automated system, ensuring precise control over crucial environmental parameters such as humidity, temperature, light intensity, and soil moisture.

The heart of the system lies in the PIC16F877A-based circuit, orchestrating a seamless comparison of real-time sensor values with predefined thresholds tailored for specific plants. This enables automated control of cooling, heating, and irrigation systems, reducing the need for human intervention and offering a cost-effective solution for maximizing yields. The accompanying greenhouse monitoring and control software further enhances the system's capabilities by collecting, displaying, and recording environmental data in real-time.

The intricate dance of sensors begins with a meticulous power-on sequence, relying on the precision of the 7805 regulator to provide a stable 5V supply to the microcontroller. Sensors such as the Soil Moisture Sensor, Light Dependent Resistor (LDR), and DHT11 sensor capture environmental nuances, translating them into tangible representations on the Liquid Crystal Display (LCD). The system dynamically responds to fluctuating conditions, activating cooling fans, water motors, and adjusting light intensity to create an optimal environment for plant growth.

Notably, the system is not confined to local control but establishes a cybernetic tether to the external world through a WiFi module. This enables the transmission of real-time data to messaging services such as Telegram and WhatsApp, enhancing responsiveness and providing insights into the greenhouse's dynamic conditions. Additionally, a micro SD card module ensures the archival of historical data, facilitating post hoc analysis and system fine-tuning.

keywords : PIC16F877A Microcontroller, threshold value, LCD, Environmental parameters

CHAPTER 01 - INTRODUCTION

Greenhouses play a crucial role in modern agriculture, providing an environment where plants can thrive, irrespective of external climatic conditions. This paper emphasizes the significance of greenhouses and explores their effectiveness in optimizing crop yield. As plants require specific environmental parameters, such as humidity, temperature, light Intensity, and soil moisture, for optimal growth, an automated greenhouse monitoring system becomes essential. The integration of a control system, consisting of a PIC Microcontroller and various sensors, ensures precise monitoring of these parameters. The PIC16F877A based circuit facilitates the comparison of stored values with predefined thresholds for specific plants, enabling automated control of cooling, heating, and irrigation systems. The accompanying greenhouse monitoring and control software further enhances the system's capabilities by collecting, displaying, and recording environmental data. The inclusion a LCD serves as a user-friendly interface for real-time information display. This embedded system minimizes human intervention, making it a cost-effective and efficient solution for cultivating crops and maximizing yields. Greenhouses, as protective structures, shield crops from extreme weather conditions and pests, thereby enhancing food production. The ability to control light and temperature transforms non-arable land into cultivable terrain, contributing significantly to food security, particularly in high-latitude regions. The global importance of greenhouses is exemplified by colossal complexes like the one in Almeria, Spain, covering nearly 50,000 acres, aptly referred to as the "sea of plastics."

1.1 PROBLEM AND SOLUTION ENCOUNTERED ON GREEN HOUSE

Efficient irrigation plays a crucial role in greenhouse systems, where the provision of water is vital for the survival of plants under various conditions. Traditionally, many gardeners rely on manual irrigation, which proves to be inefficient. This manual approach can lead to either insufficient water supply, risking plant death, or excess water, posing a threat to plant health. Additionally, gardeners must consistently monitor their greenhouse to ensure optimal plant conditions.

To address these challenges and maintain ideal conditions, automated watering systems and remote monitoring are employed. The use of automated systems significantly reduces the time and effort required compared to manual watering. This not only enhances efficiency but also reduces the need for a large workforce to manage plant or crop maintenance. Temperature sensors like thermistors and soil moisture probes are integrated into the greenhouse system to regulate both temperature and watering, ensuring a controlled and healthy environment for plants.

CHAPTER 02 - LITERATURE SURVEY

This project focuses on developing an automated greenhouse monitoring and control system, offering a user-friendly solution for farmers. The growth and development of plants are intricately tied to environmental conditions, encompassing factors such as light, temperature, soil moisture and humidity. Different plants thrive under specific conditions, necessitating careful management of these parameters. The greenhouse system, being complex, requires continuous monitoring and control due to the interconnected nature of climate parameters. Changes in one factor can adversely affect others and impact the overall development of plants. The critical factors often monitored include temperature, humidity, light intensity and soil moisture. Farmers nowadays seek more user-friendly platforms to address challenges arising from climate changes.

The greenhouse system can be broadly categorized into two components: internal atmosphere and soil conditions. While internal atmosphere monitoring is common, the importance of maintaining optimal soil conditions for water and nutrient absorption is often neglected. Therefore, the proposed automation system aims to create value for producers and the national economy by addressing both aspects. This system is expected to protect crops within the greenhouse from damages caused by external weather conditions such as rain and wind. By maintaining reference values derived from built-in crop growing conditions, the system ensures that temperature and moisture levels in the soil remain optimal, contributing to the overall health of the plants.

Temperature plays a crucial role in various plant development processes, including photosynthesis, transpiration, absorption, respiration, and flowering. The growth of each plant species is significantly influenced by temperature, with different plants having specific temperature ranges for optimal growth. Below these ranges, vital life processes cease, and the formation of ice within the tissue can occur, restricting water availability for essential life processes. Monitoring and controlling temperature are crucial in agriculture, as plant enzymes become inactive and growth stops beyond a certain range. Additionally, humidity plays a vital role as it influences moisture loss from plant leaves. Plants absorb CO₂ through tiny pores, and transpiration rates decrease with higher humidity. Dry conditions can lead to moisture loss and stress in plants, impacting flower buds and overall plant development. Conversely, high humidity can promote fungal diseases. Plants derive energy from sunlight through photosynthesis, a process that affects their growth. Light also indirectly influences plant growth, as observed when comparing plants grown in normal light, darkness, or shade. Shaded plants may exhibit taller growth and larger leaves due to reduced transpiration.

Water is essential for plant growth, and the rate of water loss through transpiration depends on soil conditions, air flow, humidity, and temperature. Soil moisture is critical, and overly moist soil can adversely affect plant development.

CHAPTER 03 – METHODOLOGY

The project involved the implementation of a greenhouse control device to control, monitor and control While the desired temperature of the greenhouse is maintained by operating the cooling (fan) system at the right time by turning the water motor on or off, the soil moisture (when water is needed) is maintained and light and humidity are controlled by this circuit.

3.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DEVICE

Fig 1: Block diagram of Greenhouse Monitoring and Control system

3.2 HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

1. MICROCONTROLLER - PIC16F877A

A microcontroller (MUC) is a small computer with all peripherals such as I/O, memory all mostly in build. Microcontrollers are used in automatically controlled devices. For Greenhouse effective management, here in our paper We are using PIC16F877A Microcontroller. PIC Controller is an RISC machine (Reduced Instruction Set Computing). It constantly monitors the digitized parameters of the various sensors and verifies them with the predefined threshold values. It checks if any corrective action is to be taken for the condition at that instant of time. It has operating frequency of 8MHz. Total power dissipation by above microcontroller was 1.0W and having Voltage Operating Range VDD in between +0.3V to +7.5V. Microcontroller also has in built 8 bit ADC.

2.SENSOR

Sensor is a device which is used to convert physical quantity into electrical signal. A sensor is a device, which responds to an input quantity by generating a functionally related output usually in the form of an electrical or optical signal. A sensor's sensitivity indicates how much the sensor's output changes when the measured quantity changes. Three different types of Sensors are used in the above system, details of which are mentioned in the following table.

SOIL MOISTURE

Tolerance= ± 0.2 V at 27°C

TABLE 1 : SOIL MOISTURE SENSOR READINGS

Soil Condition	Transducer Optimum Range
Soil is dry	0 V
Optimum level of soil	1.9 - 3.0 V
Moisture Slurry soil	>3.0 V

LIGHT (LDR)

Tolerance = ± 0.1 V

TABLE 2: LIGHT SENSOR READINGS

Illumination Status	Transducer Optimum Range
Optimum Illumination	0 V - 6.9 V
Dim Light	0.7V – 2.5V
Dark	2.5V – 3V
Night	3V – 4.7V

HUMIDITY

Tolerance= $\pm 0.1V$ RH = $((V_{out} / V_{cc}) - 0.16)/0.0062$, typical at 25°C where, $V_{supply} = 4.98V$

TABLE 3: HUMIDITY SENSOR READINGS

Percentage RH (Relative Humidity)	Transducer Optimum Range
0%	0 – 0.8V
0% to 9.81%	0.8 – 1.1V
12.9% to 20.10%	1.2 – 1.45V
22.7% to 30.06%	1.5 – 1.725V
30.8% to 40.5%	1.75 – 2.05V
41.3% to 50.3%	2.075 – 2.35V
51% to 60.02%	2.375 – 2.65V
61.6% to 70.5%	2.7 – 2.975V
71% to 80.2%	3 – 3.275V
81.1% to 90%	3.3 – 3.6V
91% to 100%	3.6 – 3.9V

TEMPERATURE

Temperature (°C) = $(V_{out} / 5) * 100$ (°C / V)

TABLE 4: TEMPERATURE SENSOR READINGS

Temperature range in degree Celsius	Temperature sensor output(Vcc)
10°C	0.5 V
(10 to 20) °C	0.5 – 1.0 V
(20 to 30) °C	1.0 – 1.5 V
(30 to 40) °C	1.5 – 2.0 V
(40 to 50) °C	2.0 – 2.5 V
(50 to 60) °C	2.5 – 3.0 V
(60 to 70) °C	3.0 – 3.5 V
(70 to 80) °C	3.5 – 4.0 V
(80 to 90) °C	4.0 – 4.5 V
(90 to 100) °C	4.5 – 5.0 V

3.RELAY

A relay is an electrical switch that opens and closes under the control of another electrical circuit. In the original form, the switch is operated by an electromagnet to open or close one or many sets of contacts. Because a relay is able to control an output circuit of higher power than the input circuit, it can be considered to be, in a broad sense, a form of an electrical amplifier. we use this project 5VDC 4 Way 4 Channel Relay Module With Coupling Protection

3.3 CIRCUIT DESIGN OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

Fig 1: Main circuit (proteus diagram)

We have used a power supply of 5V, but in power supply design we will first step down 230V to 12V using LM7812 and then 12V will be stepped down to 5V using LM7805. We require 12V because at the output side we have used relays whose ratings are 5V, 10A. From the above circuit diagram it is quite evident that we have connected 3 sensors to 2 different ADC channels of PIC16F877A. We have interfaced Light sensor (LDR) to ADC channel 1, Soil Moisture sensor to ADC channel 2. We are using 8 MHz crystal oscillator for PIC, which is used to clock. A reset button is connected to the MCLR pin of PIC. The circuit also consists of ICSP pins which are connected to the controller for the sake of programming. Pins 35,36,37,38,39,40 of the LCD are connected to a pot to adjust the contrast of LCD. Various pins from ports E, D and C of controller are connected to the LCD. Pins corresponding to RD2, RD3, RD4, and RD5 are connected to the relay board. The output signal for the PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) signal, which is controlled by the input from the LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) sensor, is routed through PIN 17.

Fig 2: Relay Board

Fig3: LCD Display

3.4 PCB LAYOUT OF GREENHOUSE MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEM

In PCB layout, the tracks for the supply and ground carry a width of 1.3mm, accommodating higher current loads compared to other pins. The remaining tracks vary in width from 0.8 – 1.3mm based on anticipated current flow. A dotted line on the PCB layout signifies the ground polygon, ensuring simultaneous grounding of all ground pins. The grounding polygon can be verified using the rats nest option in the Eagle PCB editor. Distinct pad sizes are employed for various tracks, considering the associated current levels. Figure 4 illustrates the PCB layout of the main circuit board, while Figure 5 :PCB layout with components of the main circuit board depicts circuit.

Fig 4: PCB layout of the main circuit board

Fig 5: PCB layout with components of the main circuit board

3.5 SOFTWARES USED FOR DESIGN OF GREENHOUSE MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEM

MPLAB IDE:

MPLAB IDE is a Windows Operating System (OS) software program that runs on a PC to develop applications for Microchip microcontrollers and digital signal controllers. It is called an Integrated Development Environment, or IDE, because it provides a single integrated environment to develop code for embedded microcontrollers. MPLAB IDE runs on a PC and contains all the components needed to design and deploy embedded systems applications. A development system for embedded controllers is a system of programs running on a desktop PC to help write, edit, debug and program code – the intelligence of embedded systems applications – into a microcontroller.

PROTEUS 8:

Proteus 8 is an Integrated Development Environment (IDE) for electronic design and simulation. It is commonly used by engineers and hobbyists to design, prototype, and test electronic circuits before physical implementation. The software is developed by Labcenter Electronics and provides a comprehensive environment for circuit design, simulation, and PCB (Printed Circuit Board) layout.

EASSY EDA :

Electronic Design Automation (EDA) software is a type of computer-aided design (CAD) tool used in the field of electronic design. EDA software is essential for designing and simulating electronic systems, including integrated circuits (ICs), printed circuit boards (PCBs), and other electronic components. Similar to MPLAB IDE for microcontroller development, EDA software provides an integrated environment for engineers to create, analyze, and optimize electronic designs.

3.6 WORKING OF GREENHOUSE MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEM

The intricate orchestration of the greenhouse monitoring and control system commences with a meticulous power-on sequence. Upon the application of DC voltage, the system relies on the precision of the 7805 regulator to furnish a stable 5V supply to the Pic16F877A microcontroller. This marks the initiation of the microcontroller, triggering the execution of intricately programmed instructions that govern the entire system. In the realm of sensor readings, each sensor plays a distinct role in capturing environmental nuances. The Soil Moisture Sensor, a critical component, scrutinizes the soil's moisture content. The analog signal generated by this sensor undergoes a metamorphosis into a digital value through the adept Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) housed within the PIC16F877A. The result is then elegantly displayed on the Liquid Crystal Display (LCD), providing a tangible representation of the soil's moisture levels. Simultaneously, the Light Dependent Resistor (LDR) is engaged in its own sophisticated dance with ambient light levels. The analog signal from the LDR

embarks on a journey through the ADC, presenting two distinct control mechanisms. The first method employs relay-based on/off control, dictating the operation of an A/C bulb when light levels fluctuate. The second method ventures into the realm of Pulse Width Modulation (PWM), orchestrated through the 17th pin or CCP1 of the PIC16F877A. This intricate dance generates signals that traverse through an Optocoupler Dimmer circuit, intricately adjusting the brightness of the A/C bulb. Meanwhile, the DHT11 sensor undertakes the intricate task of measuring temperature and humidity. The resulting data, a harmonious blend of numeric representation, is harnessed and presented on the LCD, offering insight into the atmospheric conditions within the greenhouse.

As the environmental variables are continually monitored, the system transitions into a dynamic phase of control mechanisms. When the temperature transcends the 25°C threshold, a corresponding relay nestled within the relay module awakens, initiating the activation of a cooling fan. This eloquent response seeks to mitigate the rising temperature, creating an environment conducive to plant well-being. Conversely, as the temperature descends by 20°C, the relay retreats into dormancy, orchestrating the graceful cessation of the cooling fan.

Humidity, a delicate parameter, undergoes a similar dance of control. If the humidity stoops below the 60% mark, an astutely connected relay springs into action, setting in motion the rhythmic activation of a water motor, gently sprinkling life-giving moisture upon the flora. The saga unfolds in reverse when humidity ascends beyond the 80% threshold, coaxing the relay into deactivation and bringing a tranquil end to the water motor's endeavors. In the realm of soil moisture, the analog signal emanating from the Soil Moisture Sensor is meticulously scrutinized. Should this signal dip below the 1.9V threshold, a relay, attuned to this delicate balance, surges into activation. This triggers a series of events, culminating in the deployment of a corresponding mechanism, often associated with irrigation or other moisture-mitigating strategies. Conversely, as the analog signal ascends beyond the 3V threshold, a symphony of deactivation unfolds, gracefully concluding the operation and ushering in a phase of stasis.

Amidst these complex maneuvers, the system remains interconnected with the external world through the marvel of internet connectivity. A WiFi module serves as the gateway, facilitating the transmission of meticulously formatted data to messaging services such as Telegram and WhatsApp. This cybernetic tether enhances the system's responsiveness, providing real-time updates and insights into the greenhouse's dynamic conditions. Furthermore, the system engages in an archival process, ensuring that no detail is lost to the sands of time. The micro SD card module diligently records and stores copious amounts of data, creating a rich tapestry of historical information. This reservoir of knowledge becomes an invaluable asset, allowing for post hoc analysis and fine-tuning of the system.

In summation, the greenhouse monitoring and control system unfolds as an intricately choreographed ballet of sensors, relays, and control mechanisms. It navigates the delicate balance between environmental variables and automated responses, culminating in a symphony of harmonized conditions for optimal plant growth. This intricate dance, guided by the intelligence of the PIC16F877A microcontroller, stands as a testament to the fusion of technology and nature, creating a sanctuary for flourishing flora.

CHAPTER 04 - RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 TESTING AND RESULTS

I] SOFTWARE TESTING

In the realm of software testing, our approach involved leveraging Proteus 8 as a key tool for virtual simulation, specifically focusing on a variety of sensors in conjunction with microcontrollers. Proteus 8, recognized for its user-friendly interface, serves as versatile electronic circuit design software, encompassing circuit design, virtual simulation, and PCB layouts. Our testing methodology centered around interfacing sensors with the microcontroller, facilitating the integration of hex program files into the controller. This allowed us to closely monitor and analyze the real-time actions and responses of the system. To emulate real-world scenarios, we established thresholds within the program, enabling us to observe and evaluate the corresponding control actions. This comprehensive testing strategy not only ensured the proper functioning of the sensors and microcontroller but also provided insights into the system's responsiveness and adherence to predefined thresholds. The use of Proteus 8 as a simulation tool significantly contributed to the efficiency and accuracy of our testing procedures, ultimately enhancing the overall robustness of the software and its components.

II] HARDWARE TESTING

In hardware testing we opted for breadboard and PCB testing. In breadboard testing we checked the power supply output, all the results were positive and we got 5V at the output. We interfaced 3 sensors namely temperature & humidity (DHT11), LDR and soil moisture on breadboard with PIC16F877A to check the monitoring and control actions.

For testing purpose we used LED's to detect whether the control actions are being performed correctly or not. The results that we achieved from breadboard testing were satisfactory and convincing. With the controlling actions continuous monitoring of 3 parameters was also monitored on LCD. There were many things whose testing was not feasible in breadboard testing; we included those while doing PCB testing. First of all after designing the PCB, connectivity between the PCB tracks was checked before and after soldering of components. Then as done in breadboard testing, we checked the output of power supply in PCB also. Instead of LED's that were used in breadboard testing, here we used relays to observe the control actions. Thus it was observed that whenever there was a change in the real time values of various parameters with respect to the predefined thresholds, the relays turned ON and OFF as per programmed.

4.2 RESULTS

The greenhouse monitoring and control system, powered by a Pic16F877A microcontroller, orchestrates a seamless operation to foster optimal plant growth conditions. Initiated by a stable 5V supply from the 7805 regulator upon receiving DC voltage, the microcontroller executes programmed instructions. Key sensors, including the Soil Moisture Sensor, LDR, and DHT11, provide real-time data on soil moisture, light, temperature, and humidity. The system dynamically responds to environmental variations; activating the cooling fan when temperatures exceed 25°C and the water motor when humidity drops below 60%, and deactivating them at 20°C and above 80%, respectively. Soil moisture-based relay control ensures irrigation between 1.9V and 3V analog signals. Additionally, the LDR governs light through relay-based on/off control and PWM-based brightness adjustments using CCP1 and an Optocoupler Dimmer circuit. Internet connectivity facilitates real-time data transmission to messaging services, while a micro SD card module records and stores comprehensive data for historical analysis. In summary, this intelligent system harmonizes sensor inputs with automated controls, ensuring a conducive greenhouse environment for plant vitality.

Fig 6: Final Our Project with display

Fig 7 : Final project

CHAPTER 05 - CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 CONCLUSION

The present study provides a reliable Greenhouse Monitoring and Control System, having wide application in agriculture. In this system the sensor side acts like a data acquisition unit that is capable of measuring four different parameters like temperature, light, humidity and soil moisture. The main part is the controller which carries out various tasks like collection, data storage, data processing and greenhouse climate adjustment. Also, the database of various plants which is already stored in our system containing the necessary climatic conditions needed for proper growth of those plants will be very useful in increasing yield of crop plants. With provided and data, analysis will be very easily done and thus required changes can be implemented in system. Thus the proposed system providing real time application and is beneficial for farmers of many developing countries

5.2 FUTURE WORK & CHALLENGES

Future Works

- Integrate advanced machine learning algorithms for predictive modeling and more Adaptive control strategies based on historical data.
- Exploring wireless sensor networks to improve scalability and ease of deployment Large greenhouse settings.
- Investigating the incorporation of additional sensors or technologies to monitor and Controlling other critical parameters like carbon dioxide levels or nutrient concentration, pH value.
- Develop a user-friendly interface or mobile application for remote monitoring and Control of the greenhouse system
- Arrange solar panel for the electricity requirement of this system and add it to this system

Challenges

- We intended to control the light of the AC bulb in the greenhouse in a manner similar to how we control the light of the LDR. However, a challenge arose concerning the connection of DC and AC currents. To address this issue, we employed an optocoupler dimmer.
- In the Proteus simulation, the logic we applied to the code functioned correctly. However, during practical testing, we observed that the logic behaved oppositely to our expectations. Consequently, the code was modified once again.
- When attempting to integrate a WiFi module into the system, we encountered difficulty in establishing a direct connection between the WiFi module and the PIC. To address this challenge, an ESP32 was employed solely for the purpose of connecting to the internet.

APPENDIX (CODE)

Green.c

```
#include "config.h"
#include "lcd.h"
#include "dht11.h"
#include "motor.h"
#include "readdht.h"
#include "portinit.h"
#include "adcinit.h"

#define delay __delay_ms(5)
#define DHT11_Data_Pin PORTDbits.RD0
#define DHT11_Data_Pin_Direction TRISDbits.TRISD0

unsigned char Check_bit,Temp_byte_1,Temp_byte_2,RH_byte_1,RH_byte_2,temper,RH,Sumation;
unsigned int digit,temp;
float voltage,voltagee;

void main(void) {
    portinit();
    Lcd_Init();
    // Lcdbegin();// show things when lcd on
    Lcd_Clear();
    RD2=RD3=RD4=RD5=0;
    while(1){

        dht11_init();
        find_response();

        if(Check_bit == 1){
            read_dht();
            if(Sumation == ((RH_byte_1+RH_byte_2+Temp_byte_1+Temp_byte_2) & 0XFF)){

                set_temp_hum();

                disp_act_data();

                adcinit();
                __delay_ms(100);

                tempcon();

                moisturecon();
```

```
    humcon();  
    adcoininit();  
    pwm();  
    leds();  
  }  
}  
}  
return;  
}
```

REFERENCES

- [1] Kiran Sahu, Susmita Mazumdar (2012). Digitally Greenhouse Monitoring and Controlling of System based on Embedded System. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 3, Issue 1, ISSN 2229-5518
- [2] Thomas, Andrew L. and Richard J. Crawford, Jr. (2001). *Performance of an energy-efficient, solar-heated greenhouse in southwest Missouri*. Southwest Missouri Agricultural Research and Education Center 2001 Research Report. University of Missouri-Columbia
- [3] Gill, S., R.A. Cloyd, J.R. Baker, D.L. Clement, and E. Dutky(2006). *Pests & Diseases of Herbaceous Perennials: The Biological Approach*. Ball Publishing Co., Batavia, IL
- [4] Muhammad Ali Mazidi, Janice GillispieMazidi, Rolin D. McKinlay., “*The 8051 Microcontroller & Embedded Systems*”, Pearson Education Inc. 2nd Edition, 2008.
- [5] Gu Jinan, Mao Hanping, “*A mathematical model on intelligent control of greenhouse environment*”, *Transactions of the Chinese Society for Agricultural Machinery*, vol. 32, pp.63-66, 2001
- [6] Stipanicev D., Marasovic J. (2003). Network embedded greenhouse monitoring and control. *Proceedings of 2003 IEEE Conference on Control Applications*.
- [7] PIC microcontroller Data Sheet, Microchip.
- [8] SENSORS- The Journal of Applied Sensing Technology, Advanstar Communications Inc.
- [9] S.U. Zagade, R.S. Kawitkar (2012). Wireless Sensor Network for Greenhouse. *International Journal of Science and Technology*, Volume 2 No.3, ISSN 2224-3577
- [10] Thomas, Andrew L. and Richard J. Crawford, Jr. (2001). *Performance of an energy-efficient, solar-heated greenhouse in southwest Missouri*. Southwest Missouri Agricultural Research and Education Center 2001 Research Report. University of Missouri-Columbia.
- [11] Gill, S., R.A. Cloyd, J.R. Baker, D.L. Clement, and E. Dutky(2006). *Pests & Diseases of Herbaceous Perennials: The Biological Approach*. Ball Publishing Co., Batavia, IL.
- [12] Kenneth M. Chomitz (1998). *Baselines for greenhouse gas reductions:Problems, precedents, solutions*. Development Research Group, Carbon Offsets Unit.
- [13] Kiran Sahu, Susmita Mazumdar (2012). Digitally Greenhouse Monitoring and Controlling of System based on Embedded System. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 3, Issue 1, ISSN 2229-5518.
- [14] Leong Boon Tik, Chan Toong Khuan, Sellappan Palaniappan(2009). *Monitoring of an Aeroponic Greenhouse with a Sensor Network*. *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*.Vol.9.